

Studies on Arylfuran Heterocycles. Part-I. Synthesis of 6-(5-Aryl-2-furyl)-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles

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Manuscript received 5 October 1990, revised 5 February 1991, accepted 31 May 1991

Several 4-(5-aryl-2-furfurylidene)amino 3-mercapto-5-substituted-1,2,4-triazoles have been synthesised and converted into 1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles. These triazolothiadiazoles are also synthesised by an alternative method in better yields employing arylfuroic acids and *s*-triazoles in the presence of phosphorus oxychloride. The compounds are also tested for their antibacterial properties.

MANY nitrofurfuraldehyde hydrazones possess broad spectrum antibacterial properties and find application as commercial drugs^{1,2}. Several attempts have been made by various researchers to modify the structures of the nitrofuran drugs by introducing carrier molecules during drug design^{2,3} with a view to reduce the toxicity. One such modification is to introduce a *p*-nitrophenylfuran substituent in place of nitrofuran in drugs to be synthesised.

Triazoles and their fused derivatives⁴ are also reported to possess significant antifungal and antibacterial properties. In an attempt to minimise the toxicity, the present work reports the synthesis of a series of 3-substituted-4-amino-5-mercaptotriazoles and to condense them with *p*-nitrophenylfurfuraldehyde. The resulting hydrazones are further subjected to cyclisation to yield triazolothiadiazoles carrying nitrophenylfuran substituents. An alternative route for the synthesis of the above condensed heterocycles is also planned.

For the present work, three alkyl substituted 4-amino-5-mercapto-*s*-triazoles were prepared according to the reported procedure⁵ by refluxing thio-carbohydrazides with suitable aliphatic carboxylic acids. Three 3-aryl-4-amino-5-mercapto-*s*-triazoles were prepared according to the reported procedure⁶. In order to study the structure-activity relationship, three arylfurfurals were employed for the condensation (Scheme 1). The triazoles (2) were then condensed with the arylfurfurals to afford 4-(5-aryl-2-furfurylidene)amino-3-mercapto-*s*-triazoles (3). Formation of these condensation products was confirmed by elemental and spectral analysis. The characterisation data of the nitrophenylfuran derivatives are given in Table 1.

Oxidative cyclisation of these hydrazones employing bromine in acetic acid or thionyl chloride afforded the condensed triazolothiadiazoles (5). However, an alternative and convenient method of synthesis of these condensed heterocycles is through condensation of the triazoles (2) with 5-arylfuran-2-carboxylic acids (4) in presence of phosphorus oxychloride.

Scheme 1

Structures of these compounds (5) were assigned on the basis of spectral data.

Our attempts to synthesise the triazolothiadiazoles (5) using oxidative cyclisation of the Schiff bases (3) were partially successful, in most cases the yields were low and the work-up was tedious. Hence we carried out the hydrogen peroxide oxidation of the arylfurfurals and obtained the corresponding arylfuroic acids. Alternatively, the synthesis of these arylfuroic acids was also achieved through Meerwin reaction of furoic acids with the diazonium

salts. The triazoles (2) were then condensed with arylfuroic acids in the presence of phosphorus oxychloride to afford the expected triazolothiadiazoles (5) in good yields. All the compounds were characterised by elemental and spectral data. The characterisation data of these nitrophenylfuran heterocycles are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3 AND 5*

Compd. no.	R'	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
3a	CH ₃	NO ₂	305	85	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₃ S
3b	C ₂ H ₅	NO ₂	265	88	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₃ S
3c	C ₃ H ₇	NO ₂	246	90	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₃ S
3d	C ₆ H ₅	NO ₂	250	86	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₃ S
3e	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	NO ₂	248	82	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₄ S
3f	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	NO ₂	259	78	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ O ₃ S
3g	CH ₃	Br	284	85	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ BrN ₄ O ₃ S
3h	C ₂ H ₅	Br	240	87	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ BrN ₄ O ₃ S
3i	C ₃ H ₇	Br	231	84	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ BrN ₄ O ₃ S
3j	C ₆ H ₅	Br	275	80	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ BrN ₄ O ₃ S
3k	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	Br	240	81	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ BrN ₄ O ₄ S
3l	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	Br	256	82	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ BrClN ₄ O ₃ S
3m	CH ₃	Cl	288	84	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ ClN ₄ O ₃ S
3n	C ₂ H ₅	Cl	243	86	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ O ₃ S
3o	C ₃ H ₇	Cl	217	82	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ O ₃ S
3p	C ₆ H ₅	Cl	273	87	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ O ₃ S
3q	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	Cl	252	80	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ O ₄ S
3r	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	Cl	255	83	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₃ S
5a	CH ₃	NO ₂	215	75	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₅ O ₃ S
5b	C ₂ H ₅	NO ₂	265	78	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₃ S
5c	C ₃ H ₇	NO ₂	221	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₃ S
5d	C ₆ H ₅	NO ₂	271	76	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₃ S
5e	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	NO ₂	307	77	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₄ S
5f	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	NO ₂	289	82	C ₁₉ H ₁₀ BrClN ₅ O ₃ S
5g	CH ₃	Br	237	76	C ₁₄ H ₉ BrN ₅ O ₃ S
5h	C ₂ H ₅	Br	206	82	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ BrN ₅ O ₃ S
5i	C ₃ H ₇	Br	225	76	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ BrN ₅ O ₃ S
5j	C ₆ H ₅	Br	255	81	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ BrN ₅ O ₃ S
5k	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	Br	238	80	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ BrN ₅ O ₄ S
5l	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	Br	222	76	C ₁₉ H ₁₀ BrClN ₅ O ₃ S
5m	CH ₃	Cl	205	78	C ₁₄ H ₉ ClN ₅ O ₃ S
5n	C ₂ H ₅	Cl	215	80	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClN ₅ O ₃ S
5o	C ₃ H ₇	Cl	235	75	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClN ₅ O ₃ S
5p	C ₆ H ₅	Cl	245	79	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ ClN ₅ O ₃ S
5q	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	Cl	252	80	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ ClN ₅ O ₄ S
5r	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	Cl	215	79	C ₁₉ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₅ O ₃ S

*All the compounds gave satisfactory results for C, H and N analyses; ν_{\max} 3a 3 120 (NH), 1 600 (C=N); 3f 3 100 (NH), 1 600 (C=N); 3k 3 050 (NH), 1 620 (C=N); 3p 3 150 (NH), 1 600 (C=N). ν_{\max} (C=N) 5f 1 630, 5g 1 610, 5l 1 600, 5k 1 600, 5p 1 590, 5q 1 600 cm^{-1} .

Some selected compounds were screened *in vitro* against the *Salmonella typhi*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* at 20 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration using cup-plate diffusion method. All the compounds showed good antibacterial activity at concentrations higher than 20 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ while some compounds were active against certain bacteria at concentrations less than 20 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Uv spectra (DMF) were recorded on a Beckman 24 spectrophotometer, ir spectra (nujol or KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectro-

meter, pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) or Bruker WH-200 (270 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and the mass spectra on a Jeol JMS D-300 spectrometer operating at 70 eV. The triazoles, arylfurfuraldehydes and arylfuroic acids were prepared according to literature methods⁶⁻⁸.

4-[5-(4-Aryl)-2-furfurylidene]amino-3-mercapto-5-substituted-1,2,4-triazoles (3). *General procedure*: To a suspension of suitably substituted arylfurfuraldehyde (1; 10 mmol) in dioxane (15 ml), an equimolecular amount of the corresponding amino-mercaptotriazole (2) was added. The suspension was heated until a clear solution was obtained, then a few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid were added as a catalyst and the solution was refluxed for 3-4 h on a water-bath. The resulting solid was recrystallised from a suitable solvent, λ_{\max} (ϵ_{\max}) 3b 254 (10 600) and 370 (24 320); 3i 268 (10 170) and 340 (32 060); δ (DMSO-d₆) 3m 10.05 (s, N=CH), 13.4 (br, N=C-SH, exchangeable), 7.0-7.2 (2H, two d, J 3, 7 Hz, furyl protons) and 7.5 (4H, two d, J 8 Hz, phenyl protons); *m/z* 3a *M*⁺ 329; 3l, *M*⁺ 458.

6-(5-Aryl-2-furyl)-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (5). *General procedure*: To an equimolecular mixture of suitable triazole (2) and arylfuroic acid (4), phosphorus oxychloride (10 ml) was added and refluxed for 2 h on a water-bath. The excess of POCl₃ was then distilled off and the residue was poured onto the crushed ice with stirring. The resulting solid was washed with water and dilute sodium bicarbonate solution, and recrystallised from a suitable solvent, λ_{\max} (ϵ_{\max}) 5b 305 (7 502) and 368 (31 370); 5i 345 (37 500); δ (DMSO-d₆) 5a 7.4-7.6 (2H, two d, J 3.7 Hz, furyl protons), 7.73-7.83 (4H, two d, J 8 Hz, phenyl protons); *m/z* 5b, *M*⁺ 341; 5m *M*⁺ 368/370.

6-[5(4-Nitrophenyl)-2-furyl]-3-ethyl-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (5b). *Method (i)*: To a solution of the Schiff base (3b; 10 mmol) in dry benzene, thionyl chloride (5 ml) was added. The resulting mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 2 h. Excess of benzene and thionyl chloride were then distilled off, the residue was titrated with petroleum ether and the resulting solid was recrystallised from DMF-alcohol (2 : 1) to yield 5b (30%). It was identical with the sample (5b) prepared as per the general procedure detailed above.

Method (ii): The Schiff base (3b; 10 mmol) was suspended in acetic acid (10 ml) and a solution of bromine in acetic acid (4 ml; 30%) was added with stirring about 30 min, and the solution was set aside for 16 h. The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and recrystallised from DMF-alcohol (2 : 1) to yield 5b (45%). It was also identical with the sample (5b) prepared as per procedure detailed earlier.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for elemental analyses and mass spectral data and

S.I.F., I.I.Sc., Bangalore, for the nmr spectra. The authors also thank U.G.C., New Delhi, and Mangalore University for the financial assistance to one of them (P.M.A.).

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